

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Adetayo, Hezekiah Olufemi¹, Ademola, Femi Temitayo², Jegede, Oluwafemi Adebowale³, Areola, Taiwo Oluwole⁴
^{1,2,3,4}Departemnt of Business Administration, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

In a keenly competitive business environment, being competitively aggressive is imperative and sine qua non to the success or performance especially of the small and medium enterprises. In view of this, the study assesses the effects of entrepreneurial competitive aggressiveness on the marketing performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Both systematic and purposive sampling techniques were used to select the eight local government areas (LGAs) used for the study in Ekiti state, Nigeria. These LGAs were selected because they have the highest number of registered small and medium enterprises in the State. With the aid of proportionate sampling technique, 99, 35, 37, 29, 34, 62, 23 and 64 small and medium enterprises were selected from the eight previously selected LGAs respectively. This brings the total sample to 383. Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of a well-structured close-ended questionnaire administered on the respondents of the study. The analytical techniques employed for data analyses were means, standard deviation and multiple regression. Results indicated a statistically significant but weak positive relationship ($R^2=0.413;P=.000$) between entrepreneurial competitive advantage and marketing performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study implied that the owners and managers of small and medium enterprises should be more competitively aggressive in order to be successful and remain competitive.

KEYWORDS: Competitive Aggressiveness, Marketing Performance, Small and Medium Enterprises, Market Share, Customer Satisfaction, Competitive Strategy Theory.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The growth, development and economic prosperity of a nation largely depend on the success of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Both the developed and the developing countries of the world have recognize the imperative of SMEs to their growth and development hence they are actively engaging in improving the activities of SMEs. World Bank in Oluremi and Maku (2024) reported that small and medium-sized enterprises constitute about 99% of the estimated 19.3 million enterprises in the European Union (EU) and that SMEs provide about 65 million jobs representing two-thirds of all employment in EU. In the developing world such as Africa, SMEs constitute the larger proportion of businesses and employ a significant portion of the population especially the youth. Having recognized the unnegotiable role of SMEs to national economic development, the Federal and State government in Nigeria have respectively put in place appropriate policies and schemes to encourage the growth and development of SMEs. Such moves by the various governments include establishment of Micro Finance Banks and youth empowerment programmes which includes different skill acquisition schemes. These efforts are to increase gross domestic product, increase SMEs production output and sales revenue. Despite this intervention, SMEs contribution to the GDP is still perceived to be very low.

Duru, et al. (2018) noted that the inadequate contribution of SMEs to the state and national development has prompted various government levels to implement several initiatives. These initiatives include financial grants/loans, entrepreneurship training, youth empowerment, and agricultural entrepreneurship development programs, among others, all aimed at enhancing the performance of SMEs. Despite the incentives and preferential support provided by the government to enhance the operational activities of SMEs, it is concerning that the performance of SMEs is still perceived to be below expectations. While some environmental factors are thought to impede their growth and performance, there are claims that some SMEs' owners lack the entrepreneurial orientation needed to withstand market challenges, remain competitive, and attract more customers (Taiwo, et al., 2019). To increase the contributions of SMEs to national development in Nigeria the owners and managers must be competitively aggressive in order to

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

boost their marketing performance in the keenly competitive business environment dominated by the giants in the industry. On the basis of this, it is therefore imperative to investigate the effects of the current entrepreneurial competitive aggressiveness of SMEs on their marketing performance especially in Ekiti State. A study by Hernandez-Linares et al. (2019) revealed that not all entrepreneurial orientation qualities are equally important in enhancing SMEs' performance, as only pro-activeness, competitive aggressiveness, and autonomy were found to be significant. This assertion reinforces the importance of competitive aggressiveness to marketing performance of SMEs.

In the light of Nigeria's prevailing economic conditions, a growing number of entrepreneurs are emerging. Olanrewaju (2020) argued that these emerging entrepreneurs often enter the industry with the primary goal of merely "doing something," lacking sufficient entrepreneurial orientations necessary to enhance performance and maintain competitiveness in the market. In some cases, it is suspected that while entrepreneurs may have a conceptual understanding of the required orientations such as calculated risk-taking, innovativeness, proactiveness, and competitive aggressiveness, they may lack a practical understanding of what these entail and how to effectively utilize them. All these factors could contribute to the observed low levels of business performance.

In Nigeria, most available studies on performance of SMEs have concentrated efforts on determining the effects of entrepreneurial orientation on performance of SMEs. Also, most of the studies are confined to a single state and outside Ekiti State. As examples, studies by Arisi-Nwugballa et al. (2016) was conducted in Ebonyi State; Adegbe (2017) was in Benue State; Adesanya, et al. (2018) was in Lagos; Edamisan and Aarinola (2019) was in Akure, Olubiyi, et al. (2019) was in Lagos and Taiwo et al. (2019) was in Ondo. In addition, other studies on competitive aggressiveness such as Chinyelu and Konya (2020) was on event management firms in Port Harcourt. The study by Kabuoh et al. (2020) on competitive aggressiveness was on the market share of SMEs in Lagos, Nigeria. A study in Indonesia by Panjaitan et al. (2021) which investigated the causal relationship between competitive aggressiveness and business performance was conducted among private universities in the country. This indicates that none of these studies had singled out SMEs in Ekiti State to investigate the possible effects of entrepreneurial competitiveness on their marketing performance. This study was conducted to fill this gap.

In view of the above, the singular objective of the study is to empirically investigate the effects of competitive aggressiveness on the marketing performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Competitive Aggressiveness (CA)

Competitive aggressiveness revolves around the capability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to respond to the competitive trends prevalent in the marketing landscape. As outlined by Edamisan et al. (2021), competitive aggressiveness refers to the aptitude of business organizations to outperform their rivals in the intensely competitive business environment. To endure in the business realm, SMEs need to be aggressive in their competitiveness. As the business world consistently expands, with expansion being the goal of every business organization, the level of competition escalates accordingly.

Competitive aggressiveness encompasses the systematic approaches that organizations employ to address the continual changes in the business world that could jeopardize their survival (Olubiyi, et al., 2019). Given the dynamic nature of the business environment, management must ensure the adoption of appropriate strategies to stay afloat. The amalgamation of innovative efforts and proactive initiatives provides competitive advantages to business organizations in the highly competitive business landscape. Ranasinghe et al. (2019) asserted that competitive aggressiveness has been characterized and associated with various dimensions, including competitive responses, multi-market competition, and the impact on SMEs performance.

The strength of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in terms of aggressiveness lies in their readiness to embrace unconventional approaches instead of relying on traditional methods of competition through reactive or responsive behaviors (Fred, 2019). Reactiveness involves a direct response to match a competitor, such as providing after-sales services like delivery to customers, even at the cost of sacrificing profits to maintain market share when a competitor introduces a new product to the chosen market. On the other hand, responsiveness may manifest as head-to-head competition or a direct attack on competitors, for example, when a firm enters a market where a competitor is already present. Consequently, competitive aggressiveness becomes essential to combat the intense competition posed by rivals (Jorg & Christoph, 2020). This aggressiveness may take the form of introducing new products, processes, systems, and variations in prices of goods and services.

2.2 Marketing Performance

In modern business management, organizational performance encompasses a variety of measurements which includes financial, social and environmental measures. Broadly speaking, organizational performance is an organization's ability to achieve its set goals or objectives. Organizational performance is the outcomes, results, or measurable outputs such as profit or market share resulting from strategies, processes, actions and steps taking to achieve the results. It is the extent to which the organization is able to meet its stakeholders' needs as well as its own needs for survival purposes. According to Jorg and Christoph (2020), performance is the ultimate result of assessing efforts made towards accomplishing predetermined goals and objectives. Adesanya et al. (2018)

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

define performance as the anticipated outcome arising from a series of activities. Synthesizing these varied definitions, it becomes evident that performance is the consequence of a series of activities, reflecting the effective and efficient deployment of scarce resources to attain a desired goal.

Generally, business performance is measured on two metrics that is financial performance and non-financial performance. Combining these the two types of performance is essential for SMEs development (Seo & Lee, 2019; Artha & Satriadhi, 2023). Financial performance are those that can be measured in economic terms of monetary value and financial operations of the organization. Financial performance measures include profit before tax, profit per employee, growth in revenue, and growth in number of employees. Non-financial measures are those that are difficult to measure in terms of monetary value which include brand reputation, customer satisfaction, innovation activities and public goodwill (Nguyen et al., 2021). Non-financial performance measures include customers' satisfaction, customers' referral rate, growth in customers' base and market share. This study adopts the non-financial measures to proxy marketing performance because it is the most relevant here.

Based on the above, marketing performance is the external efficacy measure for an organization. It is an economic measure of production efficiency in relation to customer retention, customer relationships, customer satisfaction and increase in the sales volume of the organization (Usani et al., 2021; Usani & Eko (2021). Etuk et al. (2022) explained marketing performance using four major dimensions of internal processes, customer, financial and innovativeness.

Measuring marketing performance has recently attracted more attention from both researchers and industry professionals (Sampson et al., 2022; Etuk et al., 2022). Marketing performance allows marketers to assess the efficacy of their marketing efforts in relation to their plan's objectives. According to Etuk et al. (2022), marketing performance is the process of harmonising the marketing team's objectives with the tangible outcomes achieved. It is quantified by using measures such as revenues and sales volume, lead creation, customer retention, customer satisfaction, brand awareness, and customer engagement. Zulfikar (2018) illustrates that the evaluation of marketing performance gauges the effectiveness of value creation, achieved through the enhancement of innovation skills and a comprehensive understanding of market orientation.

In this study marketing performance is the organisation's efforts aimed at converting the potential customers to realized customer and retaining such over a period of time through customer relationship and customer satisfaction with a view to maintaining or increasing the customer base and sales volume. It is the totality of the outcomes of the marketer or organization's efforts aimed at attracting new customers and retaining the existing ones with a view to increasing the organisation's customer base, sales volume and profit through quality products/services, customer satisfaction and customer relationship management. Simply put, marketing performance is the realisation of organisation's marketing objectives in the target market. It is measure in terms of market share and customer satisfaction which are market-focused measures.

2.3 Small and Medium Enterprises

Small and medium scale enterprise, small scale industries, and small-scale enterprises are used interchangeably to mean a small-scale industry firm. The criteria for classification of an enterprise as small, medium or large varies from one country to another, depending on whether it is a developed or developing country. A small business for example in one country may be a large-scale business in another. Hence, there is no universally accepted definition of small and medium enterprises as they are defined differently in accordance with the legislation of different countries. For instance, USAID in its definition of SMEs classified micro enterprise as informal businesses employing five or fewer workers including unpaid family labour; small enterprises as those operating in the formal sector with five to twenty employees; and medium enterprises as those employing 21 to 50 employees (Kayanula & Quartey in Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019).

The 1975 companies Act in the United Kingdom stated that an enterprise with a turnover of less than £1.4 million was small, those with turnover between £1.4 and £5.7million were medium, while those enterprises having turnover above £5.7 million were large. It also went further to classify the enterprises based on number of employees – those with fewer than 50 workers being small, between 50 and 250 workers being medium and those employing above 250 workers were described as being large. Similarly, the European Union (EU) in 1995, defined SME as any enterprise employing less than 250 employees, and went further to break down the SME into micro (less than 10 employees, small (from 10 to 49 employees) and medium (between 50 to 249 employees). In Germany and Belgium, SMEs are establishments that employ at least 250 and 100 persons, in African countries, the average is around 200 and in Japan it is 300 (Etuk, et al. in Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019).

In Nigeria, the major criteria used in defining Small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) include number of employees, financial strength, sales value, initial capital outlay, relative size, independent ownership and the type of industry. In view of the above criteria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in its monetary policy circular No 22 of 1988 defined small-scale enterprises as having an annual turnover not exceeding five hundred thousand naira (Ali in Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019). While the Federal Ministry of Industries in 1973 (Ayo-Balogun & Ogunsanwo, 2019) defined small scale enterprises as businesses that have total capital (land, building machinery equipment and working capital) of up to ₦60, 000 and employ up to 50 persons. Based on the

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

peculiarity of this study and the area it is conducted, small and medium enterprises are those businesses employing between 5 to 10 employees, with the working capital of ₦10-20 million and annual turnover or gross income of ₦15-25 million.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 Competitive Strategy Theory/ Five Forces Theory

Competitive Strategy Theory also called Five Forces Theory developed by Michael Porter (1979), provides the basis for this study. The main thrust of Competitive Strategy Theory is that businesses operate in a competitive environment, and success depends on the ability to outperform rivals. Porter suggests that there are five forces that shape industry competition. These forces are the threat of new entrants, the bargaining power of suppliers, the bargaining power of buyers, the threat of substitute products or services and the intensity of competitive rivalry. Businesses must identify and analyze these forces in order to develop a strategy that enables them to create and sustain a competitive advantage.

The strength of the theory is its emphasis on understanding the unique dynamics of an industry. The theory recognizes that different industries have different structures and competitive forces, and that a strategy that works well in one industry may not be effective in another. The theory also focuses on creating a sustainable competitive advantage. Hence, Porter argues that businesses must develop a unique value proposition that sets them apart from their rivals and creates a barrier to entry. This requires a deep understanding of the customer needs and preferences and the ability to deliver a product or service that meets those needs better than anyone else. This implies that for a small business to be successful there is the need for proper understanding of the competitive forces in the sector of the industry in which it operates. Small businesses must understand their areas of strength and use it to their advantages.

Despite the relevance of the theory to competitiveness, some have argued that the theory overemphasizes the role of competition and neglects other factors that can influence business success, such as innovation and collaboration. Others have suggested that the theory is too rigid and does not account for the complexity and unpredictability of the business environment. Critics of the model say it's too static and doesn't apply well to quick-changing markets, among other things.

2.5 Empirical Review

In Port Harcourt, River States, Chinyelu and Konya (2020) conducted an evaluation of the impact of competitive aggressiveness on the business performance of event management firms through a cross-sectional survey. The study targeted sixty-six (66) heads of twenty-two event management firms. Utilizing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation, the study tested proposed hypotheses, revealing that competitive aggressiveness had a significant influence on the profitability and effectiveness of event management firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Kabuoh et al. (2020) investigated the impact of competitive aggressiveness on the market share of SMEs in Lagos, Nigeria. The study employed a cross-sectional survey research design, encompassing a targeted population of 8,396 owner/managers of SMEs, from which 481 respondents were randomly selected. Data analysis involved descriptive and regression analysis methods. The findings indicated that competitive aggressiveness did not exert a significant effect on the market share of the selected Small and Medium Enterprises in Lagos state.

Panjaitan et al. (2021) investigated the causal relationship between competitive aggressiveness and business performance in private universities. The study was confined to lecturers at the top 10 private universities in East Java, Indonesia, with analysis conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) on 230 randomly selected respondents. The results indicated that competitive aggressiveness had a positive and significant impact on the performance of private universities in Indonesia. It's worth noting that the reviewed study focused on universities, whereas the current study will be conducted among SMEs.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research employed a descriptive survey research design. This research design was chosen for its suitability in depicting situations in their natural settings as they unfold. The population of the

Study comprises 16,058 registered SMEs across the sixteen (16) LGAs in Ekiti State (MCIC, 2020)

Using systematic and purposive sampling techniques, eight (8) local government areas (LGAs) out of the sixteen LGAs in Ekiti state, Nigeria were selected for the study. The LGAs are Ado, Ekiti East, Ekiti West, Gbonyin, Ijero, Ikole, Irepodun/Ifelodun and Moba from which the sample were drawn. These LGAs were selected because they have the highest number of registered small businesses in the State. With the aid of proportionate sampling technique, 99, 35, 37, 29, 34, 62, 23 and 64 small businesses were selected from the eight previously selected LGAs respectively, totaling 383. Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of semi-structured questionnaire and analysed using means, standard deviation and multiple regression.

3.1 Model Specification

To achieve the objectives of the study, multiple regression was employed. The multiple regression was developed in line with the work of Etim, Adabu and Ogar (2017).

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

$$EO = f(RT, INV, AUT) \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Where:

EO = Entrepreneurial Orientation

RT = Calculated risk taking

INV = Innovativeness

AUT = Autonomy

Extending the model further, Etim, Adabu and Ogar (2017) came up with multiple regression equation as:

$$PER = f(CPA) \dots\dots\dots 3.14$$

$$PER = f(DAC, WAA, GRC, UCP, AIC, CCNT) \dots\dots\dots 3.15$$

Where:

PER = Performance

CPA = Competitive Aggressiveness

DAC = Dealing with Activities of Competitors

WAA = Watching Against over Aggressiveness

GRC = Gaining Respect from Competitors

UCP = Undoing Competitors Posture

AIC = Aggressive and Intense Competitiveness

CCNT = Combating Competitive Negative Trend

The multiple regression model was developed as:

$$PER = \alpha + \beta_1 DAC + \beta_2 WAA + \beta_3 GRC + \beta_4 UCP + \beta_5 AIC + \beta_6 CCNT + \mu \dots\dots\dots 3.16$$

Where:

PER = Performance (Dependent Variable)

DAC = Dealing with Activities of Competitors

WAA = Watching Against over Aggressiveness

GRC = Gaining Respect from Competitors

UCP = Undoing Competitors Posture

AIC = Aggressive and Intense Competitiveness

CCNT = Combating Competitive Negative Trend

α = Constant

μ = Stochastic Error Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_6$ = Gradient of the Slope

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Table 1: Respondents Perception on Competitive Aggressiveness on SMEs Marketing Performance (n=383)

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	I am always ready to deal with the activities of competitors	4.22	1.000	Agree
2	I am always aggressive in tackling my competitors	3.75	1.135	Agree
3	I have gained a lot of respect from competitors because of my polite business strategies	4.09	0.952	Agree
4	In dealing with competitors, our business typically adopt a very competitive 'undo-the competitor' posture	4.06	0.928	Agree
5	Our business is very competitive in nature	4.07	0.950	Agree
6	Our business effectively assumes an aggressive postures to combat negative trends that may threaten our survival or competitive position	3.94	1.096	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.02	0.852	Agree

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 1 illustrated the respondents' responses to the statements in the research instrument. The mean scores for all statements consistently surpassed 3.0, leading to the decision documented in the last column of the table. The analysis from the table indicated a strong affirmation from the respondents regarding the impact of competitive aggressiveness on the marketing performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The participants acknowledged that competitive aggressiveness significantly contributed to the success of small and medium enterprises in their respective businesses. Additionally, the respondents agreed that small and medium enterprises are always prepared to address the activities of competitors. The overall evaluation of the function of competitive aggressiveness yielded a grand mean of 4.22.

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 2: Respondents Perception on SMEs Performance (n=163)

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Increase in innovation rate draws the attention of customers to my business	4.53	0.669	Agree
2	My business occupies a greater percentage of the market in the sector in which it operates	4.22	0.801	Agree
3	My customer feel satisfied with my product or services	4.28	0.959	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.34	0.810	Agree

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 2 presented the respondents' reactions to the statements in the research instrument. The mean responses for all statements consistently exceeded 3.0, resulting in the decision recorded in the last column of the table. The analysis from the table indicated a strong affirmation from the respondents regarding the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria, specifically in terms of innovation rate, market share, and customer satisfaction. The participants concurred that these factors significantly contributed to the success of small and medium enterprises in their respective businesses. Additionally, the respondents agreed that an increase in innovation rate captures the attention of customers for their business. The overall assessment of small and medium-scale enterprise performance yielded a grand mean of 4.34.

4.2 Test of Hypothesis

Ho: Competitive aggressiveness has no significant effect on the performance of small and medium scale enterprise in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 3: Competitive Aggressiveness and Small and Medium Scale Enterprise Performance

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	Std Error	T value	P Value
	0.561	0.413	0.408				
Competitive Aggressiveness				.497	.060	6.598	.000
Constant				2.613	.258	10.142	.000
F cal= 43.538 F tab = 1.960							

Source: Data Analysis (2025)

The initial objective of the study, focusing on competitive aggressiveness and its impact on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, underwent multiple regression analysis. As presented in Table 3, the regression coefficient between small and medium-scale enterprise performance and the explanatory variable (competitive aggressiveness) exhibited a positive value of 0.561. This indicates that competitive aggressiveness has a very strong positive effect on small and medium-scale enterprise performance, suggesting a positive impact of the explanatory variable on performance. The coefficient of multiple determinants (R²), standing at 0.413, signifies that the explanatory variable (competitive aggressiveness) can account for 41.3% of the variation in small and medium-scale enterprise performance. The remaining 58.7% of the variation can be attributed to stochastic variables or other factors not considered in the study.

The adjusted R² further supports these findings, registering a coefficient of 0.408. This adjusted value indicates that after accounting for adjustments, the explanatory variable (competitive aggressiveness) explains 40.8% of the variability in small and medium-scale enterprise performance. The remaining 59.2% is attributed to the error term or other unconsidered variables.

From Table 3, the unstandardized β coefficient of competitive aggressiveness yields a positive value of 0.497 with t= 6.598 and (P= 0.000 < 0.05). This result indicates a highly significant effect of competitive aggressiveness on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises, establishing its statistical significance. The positive relationship between competitive aggressiveness and small and medium-scale enterprise performance suggests that respondents' rationale for performance is strongly and positively influenced by their competitive aggressiveness, as shown in Table 3. A higher T-value enhances the result, and the positive nature of the result signifies a positive association between competitive aggressiveness and the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. This is likely due to small and medium-scale enterprise owners or managers always being prepared to deal with the activities of competitors and gaining respect from competitors through polite business strategies.

The F-test is employed to assess the overall significance of the model by comparing the calculated F-value with the tabulated F-value, as outlined in Table 4.10. The table indicates that the calculated F-value exceeds the tabulated F-value. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that competitive aggressiveness significantly influenced the marketing performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Therefore, the regression line is stated below:

$$\text{SMEs marketing performance} = 2.613 + 0.497Cag$$

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

4.3 Discussion of Results

The effects of competitive aggressiveness on the marketing performance of Small and Medium Enterprises was gauged. Through multiple regression analysis, it was revealed that competitive aggressiveness holds substantial significance concerning the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises. The acceptance of the alternate hypothesis and the rejection of the null hypothesis were indicative of the strong and positive correlation between competitive aggressiveness and the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

This result aligns with the findings of Chinyelu and Konya (2020), who observed that competitive aggressiveness significantly influenced the profitability and effectiveness of event management firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. However, this discovery is in contrast with the study conducted by Kabuoh et al. (2020), who investigated the impact of competitive aggressiveness on the market share of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria, employing a cross-sectional survey research design. Their findings indicated that competitive aggressiveness does not exert a significant influence on the market share of the chosen Small and Medium Enterprises in Lagos State. Additionally, Adesoga, (2018) disclosed that competitive aggressiveness yields a positive and significant impact on the competitive advantage of SMEs. Their research explored the effect of competitive aggressiveness on the competitive advantage of SMEs in Ogun State, Nigeria, utilizing a descriptive survey research design.

5. CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The study heightened the imperativeness of competitive aggressiveness to the marketing performance of small and medium enterprises. The results of the regression analysis indicated a statistically significant and positive effects of competitive aggressiveness on the marketing performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study empirically concluded that significant and positive relationship exist between being competitive aggressive and marketing performance of businesses. Thus a unit increase in the owners/managers competitive aggressiveness let to a significant positive increase in the marketing performance of SMEs in a highly competitive business environment.

From the outcome of the study, it implied that small and medium business owners/managers should improve and pay more attention to being competitive aggressive. Small business owners should take time to understand the activities of the competitors and device means to counter every move by the competitors which may negatively impact on their business success. Similarly, owners/managers of small businesses should constantly introduce new and novel products/services to the market with a view to dominating the market, increase their customer base and enjoy competitive advantage in the sector in which they operate.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adegbe, O. B. (2017). The impact of entrepreneurial orientation on small business performance in Makurdi, Benue State – Nigeria. Department of Business Management, Benue State University, Makurdi. 244-253.
- 2) Adesanya, O. D., Iyiola, O. O., Borishade, T. T., Dirisu, J. I., Olokundun, M. A., Ibidunni, A. S., & Omotoyinbo, C. A. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation and business performance of non-oil exporting SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 22(3), 23-35.
- 3) Adesoga, A., Olalekan, A. & Taiwo, A. (2018). Effect of competitive aggressiveness on competitive advantage of selected Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Ogun State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management* 10(35), 1-12.
- 4) Arisi-Nwugballa, E. A., Elom, M. E., & Onyeizyge, C. U. (2016). Evaluating the relevance of the dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation to the performance of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(3), 221-230.
- 5) Artha, B., Satriadhi, B. (2023). Performance of business: a review of the literature. *Jurnal Ekonomi LLDikti Wilayah 1 (JUKET)*, 3(2), 41-47.
- 6) Ayo-Balogun, A. O., & Ogunsanwo, A. O. (2019). Impact of small and medium enterprises on the growth of Nigerian economy, 1st National Conference of WITED, Ilaro Chapter. The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro August 13-16, 371-382.
- 7) Chinyelu, A. O., & Konya, K. T. (2020). Competitive aggressiveness and business performance of event management firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 8(1):99-108.
- 8) Duru, I. U., Ehidihamen, P. O., & Chijioke, N. J. (2018). Role of entrepreneurial orientation in the performance of small and medium enterprises: evidence from federal capital territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 6(1), 1-21.
- 9) Edamisan, O., & Aarinola, A. O. (2019). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of hospitality industry. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(2), 58-65.
- 10) Edamisan, O., Oyewale, J. O., & Ajayi, M. O. (2021). Influence of entrepreneurial orientation on the profitability of real estate firms in South West, Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Economic Studies*, 2(1), 16-27.

Investigating the Effects of Competitive Aggressiveness on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria

- 11) Etuk, S.G. Usani, N. E. Udoh, I. S. (2022). Micromarketing and customer satisfaction of transportation networking companies in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, *Journal of Humanities Insights*, 6 (3): 22-35. DOI: 10.22034/JHI.2022.331222.1058
- 12) Fred, P. O. (2019). The impacts of entrepreneurial orientation on the profitability growth of construction firms in Tanzania. *1(7)*, 1-12.
- 13) Hernandez-Linares, R., Kellermanns, F. W., Lopez-Fernandez, M. C., & Sarkar, S. (2019). The effect of socioemotional wealth on the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and family business performance. *Business Research Quarterly*, 1–17.
- 14) Jorg,F., & Christoph, L. S. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurial orientation on the performance and speed of internationalization. *Journal of entrepreneurship, management and innovation*,2(1), 1-18.
- 15) Kabuoh, M. N., Iwuchukwu, R. C., Onyia, V. A. &Akintaro, A. A. (2020). Competitive aggressiveness and market share of selected Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Lagos State Nigeria. *The journal of social sciences research*, 6(5), 576-585.
- 16) Nguyen, P. V., Huynh, H. T. N., Lam, L. N. H., Le, T. B., & Nguyen, N. H. X. (2021). The impact of entrepreneurial leadership on SMEs' performance: the mediating effects of organizational factors. *Heliyon*, 7(6). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07326>.
- 17) Olanrewaju, E. A. (2020). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of banks in Nigeria. *Social science Journal*, 12(4), 1-24.
- 18) Olubiyi, T. O., Egwakhe, A. J., Amos, B.,& Ajayi, A. A. (2019). Effect of entrepreneurial orientation (EO) on the profitability of SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 21(6), 42-54.
- 19) Oluremi D.O. & Maku O.A. (2024) Small and Medium Scale Enterprises and Nigeria Economic Growth, *International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 12(5), 71-89
- 20) Panjaitan, H., Cempena, I. B., Trihastuti, A.,&Panjaitan, F. A. B. K. (2021). The Effect of Competitive Aggressiveness on Business Performance: A Case Study of Private Universities in Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business Vol 8 No 4 (2021) 0875–0884*.
- 21) Porter, M. E. (1979). *How Competitive Forces Shape Strategy*. Harvard Business Review Mar./Apr. 1979. Print.
- 22) Ranasinghe, H. K., Yajid, M. S., Khatibi, A. & Azam, S. M. (2019). Individual entrepreneurial orientation and graduate business performance of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura in Sri Lanka. *Journal of Management, Marketing and Logistics (JMML)*, .6(1), 44-61.
- 23) Sampson, E. A., Etuk, S. and N. E. Usani (2022). Service quality and patient satisfaction in public hospitals in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Marketing and Management*, I (1):141-150.
- 24) Seo, Y. W., & Lee, Y. H. (2019). Effects of internal and external factors on business performance of start-ups in South Korea: The engine of new market dynamics. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, 11, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1847979018824231>.
- 25) Taiwo, A., Adesoga, A., & Olalekan, A. (2019). Effect of entrepreneurial orientation on performance of selected Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Ogun State Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 8(1) 16-27.
- 26) Usani, N. E., & Eko, H. A. (2021). Personal selling strategy and firms' productivity: A study of selected microfinance banks in Calabar, Cross River State. *International Journal of Marketing and Business Communication*, 10 (3): 30-36.
- 27) Usani, N.E., Etuk, S.G., Ekpenyoung, V. (2021). Integrated marketing communication and marketing performance of hotels in Calabar, Cross River State. *World Academics Journal of Management* 9(4), 33-38.
- 28) Zulfikar, R. (2018). Marketing performance influenced by market orientation thro-ugh value creation. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 225: 291-297.